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ZCCHC24 controls luminal fate choice.

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We conducted an expression screen to identify genes that regulate lineage specification between the luminal A and B subtypes. We identified ZCCHC24 as a conserved regulator of luminal fate choice. ZCCHC24 was activated in luminal A subtype but relatively silenced in the luminal B subtype. The data describe the importance of a zinc finger nuclear protein as a lineage determining factor in human cancer.